

THE EFFECT OF THE RELIGIOUS PILGRIMAGE ON SOCIAL NORMS AND IDENTITY

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Abstract. This paper endeavours to guide readers towards an unexplored location pertaining to Spiritual Pilgrimage. This study briefly focuses on the implementation of positive transformative changes in the lives, personalities, and social interactions of individuals, irrespective of their religious affiliations, through a divine expedition. Furthermore, it has been elucidated by the present author how the notion of Religious Pilgrimage correlates with the concept of Democracy.

Keywords: Religious pilgrimage, social norms, identity, democracy.

Аннотация. Эта статья пытается направить читателей к неизведанному месту религиозного паломничества. Это исследование вкратце фокусируется на положительных изменениях в жизни людей, личностях и социальных отношениях людей, независимо от их религиозной принадлежности, благодаря божественному путешествию. При этом автор объясняет, как понятие религиозного паломничества связано с идеей демократии.

Ключевые слова: Религиозное паломничество, социальные нормы, идентичность, демократия.

Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqola o'quvchilarni diniy ziyoratga tegishli bo'lgan tadqiq etilmagan manzilga tomon yo'naltirishga harakat qiladi. Bu tadqiqot ilohiy sayohat orqali kishilar hayotidagi, shaxsiyatidagi va shaxslarning, diniy mansubligidan qat'iy nazar, o'zaro ijtimoiy munosabatlaridagi ijobiy o'zgarishlarga qisqacha diqqat qaratadi. Shu bilan birga, qanday qilib diniy ziyorat tushunchasi demokratiya g'oyasi bilan o'zaro bog'liqligi mazkur muallif tomonidan tushuntirib beriladi.

Kalit so'zlar: Diniy ziyorat, ijtimoiy me'yorlar, o'zlik, demoktatiya.

Introduction

The interpretation of pilgrimage is contingent upon an individual's cultural and religious upbringing. Nonetheless, it is paramount to direct attention towards probable associations that may arise from embarking on a spiritual expedition. Upon investigating the relationship between Pilgrimage and the ethical concepts of moral values (i.e. good and bad) and social standards (i.e. right and wrong), it has been discovered that Pilgrimage has a significantly positive impact on them and individuals. This study has revealed that the Religious Pilgrimage phenomenon bears resemblances to an authentic democratic system. Through this research, we endeavour to pave new paths towards a better understanding of the impact of Religious Pilgrimage.

This paper aims to provide a comprehensive exploration of the profound effects of Religious Pilgrimage on Social Norms and Identity, and to offer insights into the lasting transformative changes experienced by individuals.

Pilgrimage and Pilgrim

The concept of pilgrimage has distinct interpretations depending on the cultural and religious context, but this segment concentrates on the ideas of "pilgrimage" and "pilgrims", and examines the probable connection to a spiritual expedition and its potential consequences.

According to Greenia, the field of Pilgrimage Studies continues to manifest itself in our lives as a new model in a broader sense than historical and religious criterion. One example is how sociologists study the influence and development of different social classes by analysing religion. At the same time, anthropologists use the identical set of information to analyse the cultural aspect of "pilgrimage". Art specialists could analyse the sculpted sirens and mermaids decorating pilgrimage churches differently; as vestiges of classical art, signs of temptation according to theological beliefs, and character prototypes of nearly extinct popular legends as indicated by folklore scholars (2018).

Additionally to these, Esteve Secall and González Ruiz confirm that the association between the terms religion and tourism did not occur until the latter part of the 1900s (2002). Pilgrimages have been present in the history of humanity since its early beginnings, but it is relatively recently that the concept of pilgrimage has been associated with tourism (Serrallonga, 2020). Yet, Silvia Serrallonga also puts the fact that conducting a survey among travellers who undertook the pilgrimage to Santiago de Compostela, it was observed that none of the pilgrims identified themselves as tourists.

Despite varying approaches to the study of pilgrimage, religion is ultimately and consistently at its core. A more refined and nuanced explanation relating to our subject matter can be observed through the exposition proffered by George Greenia: "Religious studies is the most obvious home of research on pilgrimage but increasingly in a fresh, non-sectarian and comparative way". He also emphasises: "That belief implies that there's something greater than the individual and his or her community (2018). Thus, people embark on this path in the desire to gain the approval of God above them, to find their identity and to pour out their faith. In some religions, such as Islam, this is a mandatory obligation, while in other religions, it is a voluntary practice. Also, changings in pilgrims' mental, emotional, and physical states encompass significant, beneficial, and enduring modifications.

However, Figure 1 bellow (Johnmeyer & Xu, 2022) represents the research result that sacred way travellers have various purposes on having pilgrimage – in Comino de Compostela – such as long-distance walking; being in nature; community; religion/spirituality; simplicity; challenge; multiculturalism; and art, history, and culture:

This singular statistic in Comino (Spain) serves as evidence that not all individuals undertaking a pilgrimage develop a sense of piety.

We can finalize that, although the word "Pilgrimage" is typically associated with religion, it can fulfil certain individuals' needs beyond spiritual reasons while vast majority of sacred way walkers do not consider themselves under the name of "Tourist", but "Pilgrim".

Social Norms and Identity

The subsequent discourse presents an in-depth comprehension of the constructs of Social Norms and Identity, elucidating their association with the principles of morality represented by the notions of "good and bad" and "right and wrong." It is impossible to conceive of a functioning society or nation in the absence of social norms, because it has significant role to maintain peace in society for its stability by "what is required, allowed, or forbidden". Conversely, the notion of "Identity" involves grappling with the concept of positive and negative, good and bad that has common boundary with morality.

According to the perspectives of Kelly and Davis, the defining characteristic of a normative proposition "allows us to distinguish normative from normal. good and bad from right and wrong. In short, norms imply "oughts," and "oughts" imply punishment and reward". On Bicchieri's picture, social norms are rules that govern the behaviour of individuals, in turn creating group-level regularities. People may conform to a social norm for different reasons: some may do it to avoid the consequences of breaking it, while others may do it simply because it aligns with their personal beliefs and values, and not for any utilitarian purpose (as (2017). On the contrary, the term "Identity" was defined by the prominent philosopher Locke as the theory "that can accommodate the possibility of life after bodily death, because the Bible reveals that there will be an afterlife". He believes that in the context of morality, the categorization of law delineates three distinct types including: divine law, civil law, and the law of opinion and reputation. Taking his Religious beliefs toward Judgement Day into consideration, one can manifest openly that in his Essay Locke argues that divine law "is the only true touchstone of moral Rectitude" (Boeker, 2015).

As it is being clear, social norms represent the commonly accepted standards determining the correct or incorrect behaviour of individuals within society. Conversely, the concept of Identity adheres to the principles of morality and immorality established by a divine power.

Pilgrimage as Democracy

Shifting our viewpoint considerably, let us examining the concept of pilgrimage and its benefits on one's self and adherence to societal norms, drawing parallels with genuine democracy.

We (as a people society) desire the presence and companionship of those around us. As reported by Hume, selves are social creatures and "[a] perfect solitude is, perhaps, the greatest punishment we can suffer. Every pleasure languishes when enjoy'd a-part from company, and every pain becomes more cruel and intolerable." (Boeker, 2015).

It is imperative that one considers the insightful points presented by Greenia, as they hold significant value: "Being a doctor, husband, class clown, nun, flirt or cop are all social roles with a heavy roster of behaviours and boundaries, specific ways to speak and act and dress and consume and interact with one's environment. All those 'secular,' off-trail forms of ego definition tend to melt away while on pilgrimage" (2018). He maintains the idea of people's equity and equality regardless their different social status. As an instance, dress code is enforced to return to oneself, with no jewellery or personal adornments allowed. Personal pleasures, such as alcohol or sex, are avoided to avoid hindrances to enlightenment. Pilgrims uphold a noble standard of behaviour, showing spontaneous kindness and even heroic protection. Some even put their own well-being and journey at risk for the sake of others. Is not the present model of democracy employing the

notion of equality as given in the examples above? Moreover, this all refers to the integrated point of both social norms and identity which pilgrimage itself contributes big role in it. As stated in Johnmeyer and Xu, following by religious pilgrimage, adopting a simpler lifestyle, the majority of individuals experienced elevated levels of contentment and fulfilment in their daily lives, including a heightened sense of independence, capability, and social connection. The majority of individuals experienced greater happiness after transitioning towards a more straightforward lifestyle (2022) According to Crane & Searle's research, stressors that are characterized as "challenges" (during the pilgrimage) have a positive correlation with several advantageous work outcomes such as improved resilience, reduced overall stress, job satisfaction, employee retention, motivation, performance, and energy levels among variety of work environments (2016).

Additionally, even brief strolls through natural surroundings can produce favourable results. An instance of this would be study conducted in 2009 by Mayer et.al, taking a brisk walk for only 15 minutes can greatly enhance feelings of positivity, sharpen one's focus, and enable them to introspect and attain a broader outlook towards their personal issues. The authors also clarified that art, history, and culture exposure increases knowledge about oneself, issues, ideas, and culture and one's place in the world. Consuming art is linked to prosocial traits and behaviour. Sociodemographic factors predicting prosocial behaviour: gender, education, religion, health, openness, and extraversion. Art can have significant positive effects, from momentary joy to lasting transformation (Johnmeyer & Xu, 2022).

Although we may characterize one person as witty, generous, a serious swimmer and good cook; another as selfish, beautiful, and an ambitious dancer; and someone else as having a strong sense of justice, being open-minded, a devoted scholar and talented piano player (Boeker, 2015), They all have the same door, same path and basically the same preconditions which connect them with each other and remind them about their inner power. With Greenia's words: "A convergence of morals brings about an unusual sense of peace and confidence among people who are unfamiliar with one another" (2018).

Given the information presented so far, it can be inferred that engaging in religious pilgrimage serves as a vital avenue for establishing harmony among participants within oneself and the larger community, transcending differences in race, religion, lineage, gender, and social standing. Hence, it could serve as an evident instance of democratic principles.

Conclusion

Briefly stated, regardless of one's affiliation with a religious caste, individuals consider themselves as pilgrims traversing the celestial trajectory. One notable aspect pertains to individuals, in spite of their social status, not perceiving themselves as superior or inferior to their peers. Consequently, the equanimity essential for the maintenance of societal standards is attained, both during and subsequent to the sacred expedition. Simultaneously, it was noted that a significant restoration of both societal norms and fundamental integrity had occurred on a vast magnitude.

Consequently, in the capacity of an adherent pilgrim, it is my aspiration and conviction that individuals ought to engage in this ritual at least once in their existence and experience the subordinate expedition within the overarching expedition denoted as "life". As we should take into consideration: "Pilgrimage is not seen as an ending point but as a starting one, it helps participants to find the path to inner peace, but they must continue working (or walking) this path" (Serrallonga, 2020).

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